

THE PROCESS OF CREATING A DATABASE OF DIVERGENT TECHNOLOGIES OF ENTERPRISES

Utkirov Anvar Utkirovich

Independent researcher of Karshi State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13342147>

Abstract: This article examines the process of creating a database of divergent technologies for enterprises. The database plays an important role in managing technological processes and increasing the efficiency of the enterprise. The possibilities of data collection, analysis and management through the use of digital technologies and information systems are analyzed. Ways to increase competitiveness of enterprises through the introduction of innovative technologies are also highlighted.

Keywords: Divergent technologies, database, enterprises, technological processes, information systems, digital technologies, data management, innovative development.

Let's start our review of the management system with the managed object. As a result of the implementation of the production process related to time consumption and resource regeneration, the management objects, having resources, direct some set of results of m_2 to the output. Information about the state of input g_1 and output g_2 , the conditions described by the external environment, and the requirements imposed by higher authorities comes to the control unit. The information block records the state of the control object in accordance with the program included in it, collects and registers information, performs its preliminary processing, including a number of elementary logical and computational operations, such as classification, grouping, reporting.

The control unit processes information and converts some sent information flow into a resulting flow, develops a series of decisions related to the impact on the access of the controlled object, and interacts with the middle environment and high-level control units.

In this case, the control unit uses information from the control object, the external environment, and the higher control level. In case of abnormal performance, the control unit makes a decision and chooses the appropriate measure to eliminate the abnormality. The control unit has a memory for developing methods of influence (it can include expert memory, electronic memory) and a control criterion (the improvement or deterioration of the parameters of the controlled object is determined according to the criterion).

At a higher level, the control unit receives information about the state of the system under consideration through the communication channel a2, develops certain decision edges (spectrum) and gives the necessary influence to the control unit through the communication channel a1. This effect may cause some changes in the system performance algorithm in question, in the order of indicator reporting, in the criteria that evaluate the operation of the managed object.

The control unit, on the basis of information from the external environment, takes into account such predictions when predicting the possible state of the environment and influencing the controlled object, as well as when creating interaction between the functional blocks of the control system itself. will have the opportunity.

Picture 1. The composition of the management system.

Thus, management represents the information process from the point of view of form. The essence of management consists in processing all the information received in the management system, making decisions and providing the resulting information to management objects in the form of a controlled effect.

Figure 2 shows the development of a controlled exposure to a control object. Decision making is done by people (work) and machines (machine action). It should be noted that actions are not related to management. It is the performance of the labor process or the actions performed by the machines.

The process of implementing management can be expressed in the information sense by the following formula:

$$O_i(t) \xrightarrow{A \begin{matrix} \text{inp} \\ \text{inp} \end{matrix}} O_i(t+1) \quad \rightarrow \quad \rightarrow \quad \rightarrow$$

where: $O_i(t)$ is the position of i - controlled object at time t ;

$\text{inp}(t)$ – information reflecting the state of i -controlled object at time t ;

A - the calculation algorithm of the management task formed for the i - object based on the information $\text{inp}(t)$;

inp – i – necessary information for making decisions in managing the facility (management influence at time t);

$O_i(t+1)$ is the state of the controlled object at time $(t+1)$ after the control action.

The given formula determines the description, composition and sequence of organization of the information system that provides the management process.

External Information Internal

2 - picture. Development diagram of managerial influence.

The following three main management levels are distinguished. The top level defines the main path (planning outline) of the system for a larger or smaller perspective. At the middle level, the structure that implements the given

strategic direction is formed or changes its appearance (organizational outline). It ensures that the system can be in the proper mode by eliminating the deviations that occur at the lower level. In this model, the interaction between the control part and the control object is clearly invisible.

They receive commands in three different forms, namely: a program that executes without any instructions; organizational rules to be followed in the event of the occurrence of certain probable events; control commands related to the expected environmental effects and deviations from the normal mode of system operation.

Below we will consider the practical nature of the operation of the full management period.

1. Forecasting is the processing of data in order to determine the possible state of the external environment, the behavior of the controlled object, and the assessment of the probability of each of them.

2. Planning is the development of the desired future state of the system (developing a planning model) and making decisions regarding the distribution of funds to achieve this state. Planning includes the selection of goals and criteria. Management efficiency is evaluated against this goal and criteria.

3. Implementation of the programming plan, that is, development of programs describing the sequence of controlled actions and their interaction for the development of the system activity algorithm.

4. Organization - one or another rule, procedure, method used to change or view the structure of stable (durable) objects or processes, that is, in certain cases, to regulate the activity of managed objects, means to define or change algorithms.

5. Normalization - continuous collection of statistical data representing the characteristics of the system and, based on them, ensuring that the system operates according to a standard.

6. Recording consists of recording a set of parameters of the controlled object and the external environment. It again involves the initial processing of incoming data, including arithmetic and logical operations such as classification, grouping, etc.

7. Control - consists in determining the content of information about deviations from normal operation of controlled objects.

8. Control - decision-making in order to eliminate deviations from the standard plan of system work due to random effects, i.e. correction based on

feedback, according to changes in qualitative and quantitative measures of the obtained effect to the managed object is to show a secret.

9. Analysis - in studying the current state of the system, it consists in analyzing its possibilities to increase the work efficiency

References:

1. Ishmuhamedov A.E. va bosh. Milliy va xalqaro iqtisodiyot: Darslik. - T.: 2010.-316 b.
2. Максимова В.Ф. Микроэкономика: учебник. - М.: Маркет ДС, 2010.-368 с.
3. В.Я. Горфинкеля, В.А. Швандара. Экономика предприятия. Учебник для вузов. - М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2007.- 456 с.
4. Фаррух Қодиров. АҲОЛИГА ТИББИЙ ХИЗМАТ КЎРСАТИШДАН ОЛИНГАН ДАРОМАД ВА ХАРАЖАТЛАРНИ ИМИТАЦИОН МОДЕЛИ. TOSHKENT DAVLAT IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI "O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ILMIY. 922
5. Qodirov, F. E. "Methodological aspects and importance of development of medical services through econometric modeling and forecasting options."
6. Фаррух Қодиров. Аҳолига хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасининг моделлаштиришни тизимли имитация қилиш. Biznes-Эксперт. 2022, Biznes-Эксперт ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ 1736 №56 ст 102-106
7. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "CREATION OF ELECTRONIC MEDICAL BASE WITH THE HELP OF SOFTWARE PACKAGES FOR MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." Conferencea (2022): 128-130.
8. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "IMPORTANCE OF KASH-HEALTH WEB PORTAL IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE REGIONS." Conferencea (2022): 80-83.
9. Qodirov, Farrux, and Muxlisa Mavlonova. "RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HUDUDLARDA XIZMAT KO 'RSATISH TURLARINI OSHIRISH." Молодые ученые 2.6 (2024): 110-113.

